

Carnatic Legend M.S.Subbulakshmi – A Study

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Abstract

The Proposed research is an attempt to study the contribution of M.S. Subbulakshmi. The most important is to know how her contribution to Carnatic works to the public because Carnatic music has a long cultural history. So the study has a social relevance to highlight the sense of appealing the music and tries to focus the practical barriers in the realm of her life in music.

Introduction

Indian classical music was identified with the North Indian gharanas. Carnatic music remained a regional Passion. The picture changed with M.S.Subbulakshmi, the golden voiced singer from the city of Madurai. Her genius and efforts popularised Carnatic music all over India and abroad. The origins of South Indian Music are traced to prehistoric times. Musical instruments form a favourite for sculptors, painters and the authors of ancient Tamil and Sanskrit texts.

Origin of Carnatic Music

The origin of Carnatic music, or the South Indian classical music often called as Karnataka Sangitham can be traced back to the age of Vedas. Bharata's Natya Sastra form around the 5th century A.D., and Saranga Deva's Sangita Ratnakara from the early 13th century A.D., are considered to be the earliest recorded documents available on the theory and performance of Indian classical music, especially Carnatic music (Karnataka Sangeetham). The history of Carnatic music or Karnataka Sangeetham is incomplete without starting about the contributions made by the saints Sri Purandharadasaru (15th century) Sri Thyagarajar, Sri Shyama Sastri (all of 15th century A.D.), had left an enduring legacy of composition. This tradition has a rich heritage and is perfectly attuned with Indian culture and religion. Carnatic music is based on a 22 scale note (swaras) on contrary to the earlier 12 note scale that is used in the western classical music.

Definition

Carnatic music owes its name to the Sanskrit term “Karnataka Sangeetham” which denotes “traditional” or “cordified” music. The corresponding Tamil concept is known as “Tamil Iasi”. These

terms are used by scholars upholding the 'classical' credentials and establish the "Scientific" morning of traditional music. Besides Sanskrit and Tamil, Telugu, Kannada and Malayalam have long been used for to song Lyrics. Carnatic music is considered one of the oldest systems of music in the world.

Importance of Carnatic Music

The most important specially of Carnatic music is its highly devotional element. The concepts of the compositions are set entirely against a devotional outline. The notes of Carnatic music is "Sa-ri-gaa-ma-pa-da-ni. These are abbreviations of the real name of Swaras which are Shadjam, Rishabham, Gandharam, Madhyamam, Panchanam, Dhaivatam and Nishaadam. Carnatic music or Carnatic sangeetham is a system of music commonly associated with the Southern Part of the Indian subcontinent, with its area roughly confined to four modern states of India: Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu. Carnatic music is considered as one of the oldest systems of music in the world.

Life History of M.S. Subbulakshmi

M.S. Subbulakshmi was born on 16th September, 1916 on the west Hnaumantharaya street in the temple city of Madurai, Tamil Nadu. According to the Tamil astrological Star Bharani are destined to rule the world. She belonged to a musician family. Her parents were Subramaniya Iyer and Shanmugavadivu Ammal. Her mother Shanmugavadivu was an established Veena artist who carried on her family's fine musical tradition. She knows that one day her beloved child-Kunjamma (little one) as Subbulakshmi was fondly called would be one of the greatest singers in the world. Her grandmother Akkammal also played the violin. She had a dream for her daughter and in due course as she watched albeit from a distance that dream transformed into reality Subbulakshmi's interest in music developed from her childhood. She grew up with her brother and younger sister in a house that is how an optician. She started learning Carnatic music at an early age and trained in Carnatic music under the tutelage of Semmangudi Srinivasa Iyer and Subsequently in Hindustani music under Pandit Narayanrao Vyas. Her mother, from the devadasi community, was a music exponent and a regular stage performer and Subbulakshmi grew up in an environment very conducive to musical learning.

Music concerts of M.S. Subbulakshmi

Subbulakshmi surprised her audience with her melodious voice and superiority towards music in the 100 pillar hall inside the rock fort temple, Tiruchirappalli. In behalf of Indian National Congress leader F.G. Natesa Ayer, the event was organised in Tiruchirappalli. In 1933, at the age of seventeen, Subbulakshmi's first performance was given in renowned Madras Music Academy (MMA). It is known as a strict and hard selection process after listening Subbulakshmi's play in the academy, to allow a young girl. This is a recording of M.S. Subbulakshmi singing the Carnatic krit "Sobhillu Saptaswara composed by Thyagaraja in the raga Jaganmohini. Another article "The M.S. Phenomenon", describes Subbulakshmi's musical talent.

Role of M.S. Subbulakshmi in Films

M.S. Subbulakshmi also acted in a few Tamil Films in her youth. Her first movie Sevasadanam, was released on 2 May 1938. F.G. Natesa Iyer was the lead actor, opposite Subbulakshmi in this film, directed by K. Subramanyam. It was a critical and commercial success. Ananda Vikatan favourably reviewed the film on 8 May 1938. All should always expect something from Subramaniam's direction for instance depiction of social Sevasadanam is one of the early films.

Shakundalai released in 1940, was a major hit. Even today, people hum its popular songs, “Premayil Yavum Marandbome (In our love, we forgot everything) and “Anandamen Solvence” (I would say it was happiness). The music drop of GVB and MS did not disappoint viewers essentially a musical, the film had some excellent visuals and of course, the romance of Shakundalai was well known.

Savithri film was released in 1941. Though uncomfortable in her male costume for the role of Narad Muni, MS carried on bravely. One of the highlights of the film was the song “Brubimubum Deti” which was to become a hit. On the day of the song recording, MS was pleasantly surprised to receive visitors – well known singers, K.L. Saigal, Kanan Bala and Pahari Sanyal. They warmly congratulated the singer and wanted Shanta Apte who played the role of Savithri in the film also became an MS fan.

After much deliberation Subbulakshmi herself chose the story of Meera. The shooting of Meera commenced in Rajasthan in 1994, with the magnificent palaces and temples of Jaipur, Udaipur, Chittor and Dawaraka forming the back drop, the film had a rich ambience. He decided to make a Hindi Version of the Film Meera.

Awards and Centenary celebrations of M.S. Subbulakshmi

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru had to say about M.S. Subbulakshmi. “Who am I, a mere Prime Minister before a Queen, a Queen of Music”. While Lata Mangeshkar called her Tapaswini (the renunciation), Ustad Bade Ghulam Alikhan termed her Suswaralakshmi (the Goddess of the perfect note), and Kishavi Amankar labelled her the ultimate eighth note of Aathuvaan Sur, which is above the seven notes basic to all music. The great national leader and poet Sarojini Naidu called her “Nightingale of India”.

During her lifetime, Subbulakshmi was honoured with some of the most prestigious and esteemed awards. M.S. Subbulakshmi was received many awards and honours. She was widely honoured, praised and awarded. Some of the popular ones include: Padma Bhushan Award in 1954 Sangeet Natak Akademi Award in 1956, Sangeetha Kalanidhi in 1968 (she was the first woman for this award), Ramon Magsaysay Award (often considered Asia’s Nobel Prize) in 1974, Padma Vibushan in 1975, Sangeetha Kalasikhamani in 1975 by The Indian Fine Arts Society, Chennai, Kalidas Samman in 1988, Indira Gandhi Award for National Integration in 1990. In 1998, she was honoured with Bharat Ratna, India’s highest Civilian Award. The award was to honour her excellence over classical Indian music and her efforts in promulgating the same both in India and abroad.

Centenary Celebrations of M.S. Subbulakshmi

Commemorating the 100th birth anniversary of Carnatic singer Bharat Ratna M.S. Subbulakshmi, the Shanmukhananda Fine Arts and Sangeetha Sabha announced a six day long performing arts and cultural festival to conclude the centenary celebrations dedicated to the Carnatic legend. The Sabha hosted grand celebration. Since the singer’s 99th birthday and is now finishing its final phase. Mrs. Subbulakshmi has been intimately weaved in Shanmukhananda’s past, with several performances of her conducted in its auditorium starting from 1963. The institution also has Subbulakshmi’s 2500 sound composition in their library, which houses over 10,00,000 recordings of Indian classical and Hindustani music.

Conclusion

M.S. Subbulakshmi was a leading exponent of Carnatic music. She was known by various sobriquets, namely, the Queen of Music, Nightingale of India, the Eighth Tone of Music and the Goddess of Perfect Note. A legendary singer, vocalist and musician, she was blessed with flawless singing capabilities that made her seem like a diva of music. Her powerful renditions of soulful music enthralled audience and transported them to a world unknown.

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